

THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPORT KARATE

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The current rules of karate were formed at the beginning of the 20th century based on the improvement of Japanese jujitsu fighting. Its initial methods and rules were developed by G. Funakosi (1869-1957, Japan). Karate players will compete individually or as a team on the 8x8 m tatami mat, and the winners will be determined based on the marks given to the techniques performed. The International Karate Federation (WUKO) was founded in 1968. It unites 157 national federations (2002), the National Karate Federation of Uzbekistan joined it in 1996. World championships have been held since 1970 (every 2 years).

Karate (or karate) is a Japanese martial art based on the hand-to-hand combat system, the doctrine of defense and attack. Learning the art of karate, people learn not so much to strike and hold blows, but to find harmony with themselves, with nature, strengthen the spirit, discover new opportunities in themselves. Karate is a philosophy, a way of life. In Japan, members of the armed forces and police are required to master the art of karate.

Karate hardens the body, trains the mind and will, makes it possible to find oneself and to know the world. Karate is based on the concept of non-violence. In some schools of karate, students take a vow not to use their knowledge to harm people. There is no historical information and facts about the origin of karate, but there are many legends about where and when this martial art originated.

Famous of karate - According to one of the legends, the founder of karate is Bodhidharma (also known as Daruma). He was the founder of the Buddhist sect of Zen Buddhism and created a certain combination of physical exercises to strengthen the spirit and strengthen the body, which became the foundation of karate. The Chinese colonists also introduced the locals to the martial art of the Shaolin Monastery. And on this island, the Chinese art of fighting merged with local varieties of fighting and a new, more advanced direction was opened. Since in Japan at that time it was forbidden to use weapons, karate remained the only

way for self-defense. The technique of warfare passed from generation to generation. Because of the deadly force, the authorities began to oppress and persecute all those who owned this type of struggle, and they retreated to the mountains. The martial art was passed down from father to son and became the secret of every master.

According to another legend, in the 15th century, China captured Okinawa and brought Chinese boxing to the island. After some time, Japanese soldiers occupied Okinawa and introduced the inhabitants to their folk types of wrestling. The local population revolted, to which the Japanese authorities issued a decree banning the carrying of weapons by ordinary people. The mixed style of Chinese boxing and Japanese wrestling helped the residents to defend themselves without weapons. Karate has developed in Asia, Latin American countries, USA, Spain, France and other countries. Karate became popular in Uzbekistan in the 80s of the 20th century. In 1995, karate players of the republic united into one federation (Karate competitions are organized in 4 directions). The Federation has branches in all regions. More than 60,000 people practice karate in Uzbekistan, more than 40 karate clubs are registered (2002). Karate players such as Ilhom Karimov, Otabek Kasimov, Sofiya Kaspolatova, Daniyoy Kholmatov, Azamat Ali Galandarov, who trained under experienced coaches such as Nurkhan Nafasov, Alisher Sodikov, and Mikhail Golovanov, won prizes in the World Cup and Asian Championships.

Until 1921, karate in Japan remained an unknown type of martial art, and only thanks to Gichin Funakoshi, a master Gichin Funakoshi from Okinawa, did the Japanese get acquainted with karate. Funakoshi was a college professor on the island of Okinawa and introduced karate to everyone during martial arts demonstrations in Tokyo. Karate technique amazed everyone and he was offered to stay and teach karate in Tokyo. Funakoshi began to teach martial arts at universities and in 1936 founded a karate school in Japan - ShotoKan.

The first karate school in the USSR was opened in 1969. But this sport became widespread only in 1991. Then a federation appeared and training courses for karate instructors began to be held. In 2017, karate was officially included in the program of the Summer Olympic Games. In some modern schools of martial art, karate is closely intertwined with religion, but one cannot speak of a strong dependence.

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